

LEVEL OF TECHNOLOGY UTILIZATION TO LEARNER ENGAGEMENT: BASIS FOR DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNOLOGY ASSESSMENT TOOL

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Level of Technology Utilization to Learner Engagement: Basis for Development of Technology Assessment Tool

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the level of technology utilization and its impact on learner engagement in the classrooms of Kinder-2nd Grade teachers for the school year 2023-2024. The study examined respondents' demographic profiles and the usage levels of various technologies in the classroom, including Educational Online Videos, Independent Online Programs, Gamified Online Programs, and Interactive Technology. Additionally, learner engagement was assessed in relation to these applied technologies. The study employed a descriptive-comparative-developmental design, integrating both quantitative and qualitative approaches. A purposive sampling method was used to select respondents, and data were collected through survey questionnaires and focus group discussions. Statistical analysis was conducted using frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, t-tests, and one-way Analysis of Variance, supported by PostHoc Analysis using Scheffe's method. Results revealed that educational online videos were the most frequently utilized technology, while interactive technology was the least utilized. Conversely, learners showed the highest engagement with interactive technology and the least engagement with independent online learning. The study found that age, sex, and years of teaching experience significantly impacted the level of technology utilization, whereas educational attainment did not. Additionally, the findings indicated that learners were more engaged when interactive technology was employed in the classroom, despite teachers' lower utilization levels of such technology. The study also highlighted challenges faced by teachers, including learners' proficiency in digital literacy and the need for an assessment tool to evaluate learner engagement. In conclusion, the study demonstrates that the level of technology utilization by teachers has a significant impact on learner engagement in the classroom.

Keywords: *technology, utilization, engagement, assessment, education*

Introduction

The massive global impact of the Pandemic shook the world as the role of the education system was challenged by Covid 19. There was a drastic change in how learning would occur remotely and reach every learner to deliver instruction. "Two years of intermittent remote and hybrid learning led schools to expand their use of some of the best-known technology tools in K12, opening the door for small and large instructional changes" (Herrold, 2022, p.1).

In an article released by the Philippine News Agency, Brian James Lu (2023) discussed the ongoing Covid-19 pandemic which seriously affected children's education, especially in the Philippines. When the pandemic started, the Philippines, along with a few other countries, did not immediately resume in-person classes to ensure safety. As a result, millions of students were impacted. While many countries have reopened schools, the Philippines has kept them closed for an extended period. When classes resumed, they used different methods like online learning and sending home printed materials. However, many students faced challenges because they did not have the right devices or stable internet connections. This situation led to what experts call "learning poverty," where many Filipino children struggle with basic reading skills. To address this crisis, Senator Sherwin Gatchalian introduced a bill called the ARAL Program to help students catch up on what they missed during the pandemic. The program will provide extra support for language, math, and science skills, involving tutors, including older students and pre-service teachers. Given the high value placed on education in the Philippines, efforts like this bill are crucial. Ensuring that children can continue to learn and thrive despite the challenges posed by the pandemic is essential for the country's future.

From 2020 to 2021, the pandemic transition time, the researcher, with a passion for teaching, found herself facing the challenge of reaching out to struggling learners in her classroom specifically to Kinder through 5th Special Education students. Despite her best efforts, traditional and explicit teaching methods often fell short of engaging these students and fostering meaningful learning experiences. Determined to make a difference, she turned to technology as a tool to enhance her teaching. Through the integration of interactive multimedia presentations, educational apps, and online resources, she was able to capture her students' attention and create a dynamic learning environment. She observed remarkable transformations as her struggling learners became increasingly involved and inspired to take part in class activities. With personalized learning paths and real-time feedback, technology enabled her to tailor instruction to meet the students' diverse, empowering them to succeed academically. As she witnessed their newfound enthusiasm for learning, the proponent of the study realized the profound impact that technology could have on student engagement and achievement, reaffirming her belief in the power of innovation in education.

With the impact and the need to employ technology, most school districts invest in software to accelerate learning, making it possible to bridge the gap from in-person teaching to remote instruction.

As the education system resumes normally, students return to school to attend in-person learning. However, new difficulties arose as students were observed to need more engagement or interaction in the classroom (Darroch, 2023).

As the researcher reflects on previous years, she has a similar observation as the school transformed from online to in-person learning. In 2019, the researcher participated in the cultural exchange program in the United States as an elementary teacher and was assigned to teach 5th-grade Math. However, in the latter part of 2020, the job assignment transformed to delivering virtual instruction to eight elementary school fifth-grade students due to the pandemic. The class utilized Google Classroom, Flip Grid, Screencastify, Nearpod, and other programs purchased by the school district to deliver instruction. In 2021, schools transitioned to the hybrid setting, where A and B classes were coming in person to implement safe distancing. The researcher taught in the classroom and applied the same technology and skills used in the virtual classroom. Integration of gamified technology and interactive online software engages learners in the school.

In the last quarter of 2021, the researcher was diagnosed with a chronic illness and had a few surgeries, leading her to be partially unfit in a regular classroom. The school district assigned her as an elementary resource kindergarten -2nd-grade teacher to accommodate the need to recover.

As a resource elementary teacher, the researcher works with Kindergarten to 2nd-grade students who have various special needs including developmental those with developmentally delayed, high-functioning autism, students with speech and language impairments, and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder. These students are in the general classroom with services provided by the researcher through pull-out and inclusion support to work on their individualized education program goals.

While the role has been challenging, the researcher has learned to develop strategies in differentiated instruction using technology to provide learners with the highest quality instruction and engagement.

The motivation surged more upon realizing how the technology was a fallback on the teaching and learning process. It significantly impacted education, whether locally or internationally. To add more, it recognized the dynamics of factors that affect the teaching and learning process in terms of learners' resources, capabilities, and motivation.

Learners of the new generation nowadays learn differently. With the evolution of different programs and software to increase learner engagement, the researcher believes a need to evaluate and assess the effectiveness of these programs and whether learners' attention impacts their progress and learning outcomes.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the impact of technology utilization on learners' engagement based on the application of various technologies in the classroom for K-2nd grade learners at Alamogordo Public Schools during the 2023-2024 school year from December 2023 to March 2024 specifically. The research focused on assessing the level of integration of digital tools, such as online educational videos, self-paced online programs, gamified learning applications, and interactive technologies, and how this influenced learner engagement. Additionally, the study aimed to develop a basis for a comprehensive technology assessment tool to evaluate the effectiveness and impact of these technological interventions on young learners. By analyzing these variables, the study sought to offer insights into the effectiveness of technology in early education settings. Additionally, it sought to provide recommendations for educators and policymakers to improve teaching practices and increase learner engagement in the classroom. Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex;
 - 1.3 years of teaching experience; and
 - 1.4 highest educational attainment?
2. What is the level of utilization in technology-integration of teacher respondents in terms of:
 - 2.1 educational online videos;
 - 2.2 independent online learning ;
 - 2.3 gamified-online learning; and
 - 2.4 interactive technology?
3. Is there a significant difference between the teachers' level of utilization in technology integration when grouped according to profile?
4. What is the level of engagement of learner-respondents using applied technology in the classroom in terms of:
 - 4.1 educational online videos;
 - 4.2 independent online learning;
 - 4.2 gamified online learning; and
 - 4.3 interactive technology?
5. Is there a significant difference in learners' engagement using applied technology in the classroom when grouped according to the profile of teachers?

6. What challenges do teachers encounter in integrating technology in the classroom?

7. Based on the study's findings, what are the basis of technology assessment tools to be developed to successfully enhance learner's engagement in the classroom?

Methodology

This section delineates the methods and procedures employed in the study, providing a comprehensive overview of the research design and the strategies used to gather and analyze data. This chapter includes key sections such as research design, locale and participants of the study, research instrument, data collection procedures, ethical considerations, data analysis, and the research methodological framework, which encompasses the research plan and schedule.

Research Design

The study utilized a descriptive-comparative-developmental design to comprehensively assess the interplay between teacher profiles, technology utilization, and learner engagement. The descriptive element gathered detailed data on teachers' demographics, including age, gender, years of experience, and highest educational attainment. This foundation allowed for a nuanced understanding of the demographic factors influencing educational technology use.

In the comparative phase, the research aimed to define differences in how various technologies were employed by teachers in the classroom.

Specific technologies examined included online educational videos, self-paced online programs, gamification tools, and interactive technologies. This comparative analysis not only highlighted the preferred technologies but also identified disparities in usage that could be correlated with demographic factors and teaching experience.

The developmental component extended these insights by evaluating learners' engagement as perceived by teachers, using the same technological variables. This approach was designed to detect any significant relationships between the level of technology adoption by teachers and the engagement levels of their students.

The primary methods for data collection in this study included electronic surveys and focus group discussions. A multifaceted approach was used to enhance the validity and reliability of the data. Interviews via small-group discussion were conducted to gather in-depth responses from participants, while classroom observations offered real-time insights into how technology was being used interactively by teachers and students.

The researcher created a customized questionnaire tailored to the specific technologies observed in use within classroom settings. From direct observations, it was noted that the classrooms utilized various forms of technology including online educational videos, self-paced online programs, game-based technology, and interactive technologies. These tools were identified not only as prevalent but also as significant in their impact on learner engagement and educational outcomes.

To further substantiate the findings, the questionnaire was designed to capture both the frequency and manner of technology usage by teachers, as well as the perceived effectiveness of these technologies in engaging students and enhancing their learning experiences. Additional data collection methods, such as focus groups with teachers and were employed to provide deeper insights into how these technologies influenced the learning environment. This comprehensive approach allowed for a nuanced understanding of the integration and effectiveness of digital tools in educational settings, thereby providing valuable data on their practical impacts on teaching and learning.

These complementary methods collectively ensured a robust and comprehensive understanding of the impact of technology on educational outcomes and learner engagement.

Participants

Respondents of the study were selected from seven elementary schools of Alamogordo Public Schools during the school year 2022-2023. Kindergarten to 2nd grade teachers were the target respondents. Purposive-convenient sampling technique was used in the selection of the respondents.

<i>School</i>	<i>Total Population</i>	<i>Sample size Teachers</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
A	10	2	20.0
B	10	2	20.0
C	10	1	10.0
D	10	1	10.0
E	10	1	10.0
F	10	1	10.0
G	10	2	20.0
	64	10	100.0

From the total population of sixty-four (64), sample sizes were determined based on the questionnaires retrieved by the researcher. The sample size for each school was calculated as a percentage of the total population, as shown in the third column.

Instruments

Two (2) researcher-made instruments were used in the collection of research data, namely: survey-questionnaire via electronic forms and Focus Group Discussion.

Survey Questionnaire via Electronic Forms:

The researcher developed a customized survey questionnaire based on the statement of the problem and needs of the study. The survey, administered via electronic forms, comprised eight pages and contained five distinct parts. Part 1 collected the respondent's profile, including gender, length of service, and highest educational attainment. Part 2 consisted of questions assessing the level of technology utilization in the classroom, specifically focusing on the use of online videos, self-paced online programs, gamified online programs, and interactive technology. Part 3 included questions related to the level of learner engagement when teachers were grouped according to profile. Part 4 explored teachers' challenges in using applied technology in the classroom. Finally, part 5 identified challenges and problems encountered in the utilization of applied technology.

The researcher used the Likert Scale to rate respondents' utilization of technology and similarly, for evaluating learner's engagement.

The survey questionnaire underwent a reliability test to ensure that the instrument consistently measures what it was intended to measure. This process involves evaluating the stability and consistency of the responses over time or across different items within the questionnaire. The reliability score .752 value of Cronbach Alpha signifies the researcher to proceed with the dissemination of the survey to the respondents.

Table 1. Mean Reliability Analysis of a Four-Point Likert Scale Instrument on the Level of Utilization/Level of Engagement in Technology Integration

Variable	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha	Interpretation
Educational Online Videos	4	.759	Acceptable
Self-Paced/Independent Online Learning	6	.721	Acceptable
Gamified Online Learning	5	.737	Acceptable
Interactive Technology	7	.792	Acceptable
Mean Reliability		.752	Acceptable

The data were analyzed using George and Mallery (2003) rule of thumb, which sets indicating the following criteria such as: ≥ 0.9 – Excellent; ≥ 0.8 – Good; ≥ 0.7 – Acceptable, ≥ 0.6 – Questionable; ≥ 0.5 – Poor and ≤ 0.5 – Unacceptable. The mean reliability analysis indicated that the instrument was acceptable for measuring its intended variables.

Focus Group Discussion

To ensure comprehensive data collection, the researcher initiated a focus- group discussion with questions on the utilization of applied technology and learner engagement when such technology was employed in the classroom. The researchers also inquired about different programs integrated during instruction and asked learners to share their experiences using various technologies in the classroom. This approach aimed to gather detailed insights into how technology impacted teaching methods and student participation.

Moreover, the researcher-initiated discussion with the teachers on their perceptions of the integration of technology in the classroom. The focus group discussion had an audio recording for transparency, reliability, and honest feedback from the respondents.

Validation of Questionnaire

Upon the approval of the initial defense, the researcher developed the survey questionnaire and sought a validator from a colleague in the same school district. The first validator is a known University Chair for Research and an expert in validating research questionnaires. He completed a Doctor of Education Major in English at Mindanao State University. He is experienced in validating research questionnaires and is currently a research professor and high school professor at Alamogordo Public Schools. Initial critique involved the verification of the statement of the problem, redundancy of questions, consistency of terms used in the study, grammatical errors, and minor comments to improve the questionnaire. The second validator completed a Doctor of Education and served as chair for research as well. She is an elementary educator in New Mexico who completed a Doctor of Education at De LaSalle University. She is also a creator of resource materials such as books and e-resources. The third validator is a Special Education Teacher who completed a Doctor of Education Major in Special Education from Cebu Normal University and has been in the education field for more than twenty years. To achieve a quality result, a standardized rubric scale was used by validators to validate the survey questions.

The survey instrument was validated through a systematic data collection process. The initial draft of the questionnaire was distributed to teachers who were not counted as respondents. Their responses were consolidated to inform the development of a second draft. This second draft was then presented to another set of potential respondents, and the results were organized and scrutinized. Responses that received significant preferences were retained, while those with minimal relevance were discarded, leading to the creation of the third

draft.

The third draft of the questionnaire was submitted to the field experts for final validation. The feedback and insights from these professionals were meticulously reviewed and integrated into the final version. This iterative process ensured the survey instrument was reliable and valid, effectively capturing the necessary data to meet the research objectives.

Data Procedure

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Data Analysis

For the accurate analysis of the collected data, the research employed SPSS version 20. The following statistical tools were utilized to analyze the data comprehensively:

1. Frequency and Percentage Techniques - Frequency and percentage techniques were utilized to identify the respondents demographic profile including variables such as gender, years of teaching experience, and highest educational attainment. These descriptive statistics provided a clear overview of the participant characteristics, facilitating a deeper understanding of the sample population.
2. Mean and Standard Deviation - Mean and standard deviation were utilized to assess the levels of teachers' utilization of technology and learners' engagement across various technological interventions. Specifically, these statistical measures were applied to evaluate the following variables:
 - Online educational videos,
 - Self-paced online programs,
 - Gamified online programs, and
 - Interactive technology.

The use of these statistical tools ensured a rigorous analysis of the data, enabling the researcher to derive meaningful insights into the

utilization of technology in the classroom and its impact on learner engagement. This methodological approach provided both a descriptive and inferential understanding of the data, supporting the research objectives effectively.

<i>Categories of Scale</i>			
<i>Scale</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>Adjectival Rating</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
4	3.51-4.00	Always	Highly utilized (5/5 instructional days setting)
3	2.51 -3.50	Often	Moderately utilized (3/5 instructional days setting)
2	1.51- 2.50	Sometimes	Slightly utilized (Once or twice a week)
1	1.00 -1.50	Never	Not utilized at all

The researcher adopted a four-point Likert scale to gauge respondents' perceptions of the utilization of integrated technology. The scale included the following descriptors:

- 4: Highly Utilized
- 3: Utilized
- 2: Rarely Utilized
- 1: Never Utilized
- 0: Not utilized at all

The Likert scale allowed for a nuanced interpretation of the data regarding the extent to which different technologies were integrated into classroom practices. By applying these statistical tools and the Likert scale, the research ensured a rigorous and detailed analysis of the data, facilitating the derivation of meaningful insights into the utilization of technology in the classroom and its impact on learner engagement. This methodological approach provided both a descriptive and inferential understanding of the data, effectively supporting the research objectives

Similarly, a four-point Likert scale was used to describe learners' engagement in the classroom when applied technology is integrated. Learner engagement was assessed based on the following descriptors: the amount of time learners attends to tasks, learner's responses and interests, disruptions due to behaviors, and instructional time productivity.

<i>Categories of Scale</i>			
<i>Scale</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>Adjectival Rating</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
4	3.26 - 4.00	Always	Highly Engaged (100 % of the class active participation)
3	2.51 -3.25	Often	Very Engaged (75 % of the class active participation)
2	1.76- 2.50	Sometimes	Slightly Engaged (50 % of the class active participation)
1	1.00 -1.75	Never	Not engaged at all

3. T-Test of Independent Samples - In the context of this study, the T-test of independent samples was employed to determine whether there were

statistically significant differences between two independent groups regarding their utilization of technology and its impact on learner engagement. This test is particularly useful in comparing the means of two distinct groups to ascertain if any observed differences are statistically significant rather than due to random chance.

Results Interpretation: The results from the T-test provided insights into whether the different groups of teachers (e.g., based on experience or educational attainment) exhibited significant differences in their utilization of technology and the resulting learner engagement. These findings helped to understand the influence of demographic factors on technology integration in the classroom.

4. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) F-test - To compare the mean differences between multiple groups and determine if these differences are statistically significant, the ANOVA F-test was employed. This test was used to assess whether there are significant differences in the utilization of technology and learner engagement based on different demographic variables such as years of teaching experience and educational attainment. The ANOVA F-test helped identify the impact of these demographic factors on the perceptions and effectiveness of technology integration in the classroom

5. Scheffe Test employed a Post -hoc Anova Test to determine how significant is the significance of the value obtained in F -Test.

Decision Criteria:

- The null hypothesis was accepted if the sig -value was greater than 0.05, indicating no significant difference between and among the groups.
- The null hypothesis was rejected if the computed sig value was less than or equal to 0.05, indicating a significant difference between and among the groups.

Ethical Considerations

The following considerations are deemed necessary for the protection of the study's researcher and participants.

1. Voluntary Participation

Voluntary participation is a cornerstone of ethical research. The researcher ensured participants should not be subjected to any form of harm and have the right to choose whether to participate or decline when approached. The researcher sought assistance from the school's ICT department and coordinator of technology for survey dissemination. The coordinator of technology sent out the form to all the respondents across the school district.

2. Confidentiality

The privacy of research participants was stringently protected, ensuring a high level of confidentiality for all data collected. Respondents were assured that the information provided was exclusively for this study and not be disclosed for any other reason. Participants were assured that their privacy would be perpetually safeguarded, and that all data be kept in strict confidence. Various confidentiality procedures were employed to uphold the respondents' right to privacy.

3. Risk

The responses of study participants were utilized solely for educational improvement. It ensured that participation in the study was not jeopardized by the participants' employment or performance evaluations. All communications regarding the research were conducted with honesty and transparency. The study did not mislead information or bias the representation of primary data findings, maintaining integrity throughout the research process.

4. Benefits

Participants received an overview of the study and were informed about the significance of its findings for the welfare of students. This transparency ensured participants understood the potential positive outcomes of their involvement in the research.

5. Nature of Engagement

Participants were told the right to withdraw from the study at any point, should they choose to discontinue their participation. This provision ensured that participants did not feel coerced and could exercise their autonomy throughout the research process.

6. Token of Appreciation

In recognition of the time and effort contributed by the respondents, a token and letter of appreciation were provided. This gesture reflected the researcher's gratitude and acknowledged the valuable input provided by the participants, reinforcing the importance of their role in the study. In addition, the researcher randomly selected winners of gift cards through an electronic spin-a-wheel to demonstrate appreciation for their participation.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the study and provides a comprehensive discussion of the findings. It aimed to analyze the data collected from the survey questionnaires, interviews, focus group discussions, and classroom observations to address the research questions and objectives outlined in the previous chapters.

1. What is the demographic profile of the following respondents in terms of age, sex, years of teaching experience and highest educational attainment?

Table 2. Profiles of Respondents

Variables	Indicators	Frequency	Percentage
Age	20-30 years old	2	6.0
	31-40 years old	13	37.0
	41-50 years old	13	37.0
	51-60 years old	5	14.0
	61-70 years old	2	6.0
	Total	35	100.0
Sex	Male	3	9.0
	Female	32	91.0
	Total	35	100.0
Years of Teaching Experience	1-5 years	8	23.0
	6-10 years	6	17.0
	11-15 years	21	60.0
	Total	35	100.0
Highest Educational Attainment	Bachelor's Degree	12	34.0
	Acquired Units in Master's Degree	9	26.0
	Completed Master's Degree	11	31.0
	Acquired Units in Doctorate Degree	2	6.0
	Completed Doctorate Degree	1	3.0

Total	35	100.0
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In terms of the profile of the respondents, the above table showed that many of the respondents similarly belonged to ages 31-40 years old and 41-50 years old. Moreover, most of the respondents were female. The years of teaching experience revealed that the majority were teaching in their school for 11-15 years. Finally, the highest educational attainment showed that many of them obtained a bachelor's degree followed by those who completed a master's degree and those with acquired units in a master's degree.

The participants primarily belonged to the middle age group, with most having grown up in Alamogordo. Following their graduation, many chose to remain in their hometown and pursue careers as educators within the same school district. This demographic detail is significant, as it highlights a community-centric lifestyle, with many teachers having their own children enrolled in the schools where they teach.

Alamogordo is a small town characterized by a close-knit community where residents are familiar with one another. The simplicity of life in Alamogordo, coupled with the benefits and retirement plans offered to educators, are significant factors influencing career choices in this region. The attractiveness of insurance and other privileges the school district provides encourages many individuals to enter the teaching profession. Additionally, the fact that Alamogordo offers higher salaries for teachers compared to other school districts further incentivizes educators to settle and build their careers in this town.

Similarly, an online article learn.org (2024) released information on the research of factors affecting teachers' age. On average, teachers in US public schools are 41 years old. The average age is shaped by the career trajectories and entry ages of educators, with some entering the profession after exploring other career options. Key considerations include retirement benefits, demographic trends, and how innovative teaching methods affect teacher retention.

Additionally, personal life experiences, such as raising a family, not only enhance a teacher's ability to relate to students but also influence their decision to remain in or leave the profession.

When it comes to sex profile, according to an article released in 2017 by the National Women's History Museum, women received 80% of the bachelor's degrees awarded in Education, leading to a predominately female pool of candidates for new teaching roles. Over 150 years ago, women started obtaining advanced degrees and were often encouraged to channel their expanded expertise into teaching. This has contributed to the enduring perception of teaching as a predominantly female profession within US culture.

According to the National Center for Education Statistics (2023), the distribution of teaching experience among educators is as follows: 7% have less than 3 years of experience, 29% have between 3 and 9 years, 37% have between 10 and 20 years, and 26% have over 20 years of experience. This data from three years ago aligns closely with findings from a recent study, where 60% of the respondents had been in the teaching profession for more than 10 years. Possible reasons for this trend could include job satisfaction, the accrual of benefits and pensions, or a deep commitment to the field of education.

Regarding years of teaching experience, many respondents held a bachelor's degree, while only three percent had completed or were pursuing doctoral studies. Vural, Ömer, Başaran, & Mehmet (2021) revealed that these reasons prevent teachers from pursuing graduate school degrees; economic conditions, limited time availability, challenges with interviews and language barriers, and issues stemming from the institution they are employed by, all emerge as significant factors. These elements play a critical role in shaping the experiences and opportunities available to individuals, often influencing their professional and personal development.

2. What is the level of utilization in technology integration of teacher respondents in terms of educational online videos, self-paced/independent online learning, gamified-online learning, and interactive technology?

Table 3. *Level of Utilization in Technology Integration of Teacher-Respondents*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Educational Online Videos	3.31	0.80	Often	1
Independent Online Learning	2.91	1.25	Often	2
Gamified Online Learning	2.57	1.01	Often	3.5
Interactive Technology	2.57	1.27	Often	3.5
Composite	2.84	1.08	Often	--

The above table illustrated that the teacher-respondents often utilized technology integration in terms of educational online videos, independent online learning, gamified online learning, and interactive technology. The findings further disclosed that educational online videos yielded the highest mean score among others. This was followed by independent online learning. The level of utilization in technology integration on gamified online learning and interactive technology similarly obtained their rank as shown in the above table.

In support of the findings, teachers share opinions on the application of videos integrated into teaching. Teachers shared the use of online videos to engage learners. They added that they utilized "YouTube" and approved district programs to find relevant educational videos to integrate into their presentation of lessons. The school district only utilized an approved educational video on "YouTube" to ensure that learners would only view appropriate and approved content for instruction. Furthermore, teachers utilize videos for

motivation, especially young learners from Kinder to 2nd grade.

Teachers play videos to introduce rhyming words, the alphabet, and secret stories of the alphabet every day for learners to retain and master phonemic awareness. Other teachers use it for guided instruction and social learning. To ensure that videos are appropriate, the information technology department filters and eliminates inappropriate content and provides teachers the opportunity to mark and report videos irrelevant to student learning making it a collaboration to ensure that there is a quality of materials presented to the class.

Similarly, Alber (2019) noted that teachers consistently aim to demonstrate rather than merely describe when introducing information, concepts, and skills to students. Education researcher Pauline Gibbons advises, "Instead of simplifying information, amplifying the curriculum involves discovering numerous methods to make crucial information understandable."

Educators frequently encounter difficulties in expanding their curriculum. Video clips can be an excellent tool to help students achieve a deeper comprehension of the material. It is significant to consider the frequency and extent of video use—it is essential to have a definitive purpose for incorporating any film, documentary, or news clip into the curriculum.

Moreover, teachers noted that videos help learners retain information using visuals and audio. They often used it to build a background knowledge of a certain concept then eventually lead and facilitate discussion and provide instruction as they perform certain tasks.

Concerning the use of Independent Online learning, respondents also affirmed that the use of independent online learning engages learners depending on the content and level of difficulty. While the utilization varies on the need to integrate it, overall, it showed that teachers often utilized this approach as a part of enrichment programs for learners. The liberty to integrate this technology differs in the teacher's assessment and the learners' needs. Based on the focus group discussion, one teacher stated that she utilized self-paced /independent online learning every day. A kindergarten teacher noted "It's like an everyday thing, we usually do "I station " and some days I let them choose whatever they want. Another teacher said that the utilization and assigning of certain independent online programs depend on their data. She would add more days using programs where students mostly score low and then use twice a week on the areas found to be low when it comes to scores from the school district's data.

I station or Imagination Station is an educational technology company founded in 1998 based in Texas that provides comprehensive e-learning programs designed to support reading, math, and Spanish literacy. It is commonly used in schools across the United States to deliver interactive instructions and assessments through its digital platform. The program includes adaptive curriculum materials tailored to meet the individual needs of students, allowing for personalized learning paths.

I station's tools are used for benchmarking student performance, monitoring progress, and guiding instruction with data-driven insights. It provides assessments that help educators identify areas where students may need additional support, making it a valuable resource for targeted intervention. The platform also incorporates engaging, game-like elements to help motivate students and enhance their learning experience. Since this is a mandated program from the school district, it is often one of the technologies used by the teachers next to educational online videos.

On the other hand, Temkin (2022) mentioned further Asynchronous instruction which takes learners' advantage of many more technology and teaching options available. He further described that this type of instruction allows learners to complete tasks and work on their phase. It allows the teacher to differentiate instruction based on which type of learning works best for them.

On the other hand, gamified and interactive technology programs were frequently noted as tools employed by teachers in the classroom. The utilization of these technologies often depends on the individual preferences of the respondents. While some educators incorporate these tools to enhance motivation or assess student learning, others express concerns about the time required to teach young learners the necessary skills to effectively manipulate these technologies.

Despite acknowledging that learners generally enjoy interacting with view boards and exhibit increased engagement, some teachers encounter challenges. Specifically, the additional time required to instruct students in using these technologies can detract from other instructional activities. This highlights a potential barrier to the widespread adoption of interactive technologies, as the time investment needed to ensure that all students can competently use these tools may not be feasible within the constraints of the classroom schedule.

Moreover, the effectiveness of these technologies is not universally perceived, as some respondents suggest that the benefits of enhanced engagement and motivation must be balanced against the practicalities of classroom management and the diverse technological proficiency levels among students.

Similarly, Saad and Simone (2023) discovered in their study that teachers perceive game-based teaching as engaging for students. However, despite the availability of sufficient devices and technology, teachers acknowledged the need for additional support and training, as students tend to adopt a passive learning approach.

Costa (2020) reiterates that the effective use of online learning is when the school establishes a regular, positive, and interactive relationship with students. One strategy to foster these relationships is through the use of videos. Instructor-generated videos have been shown to enhance student satisfaction and increase course engagement levels. Building relationships and adding engaging content with the use of technology significantly enhances the teaching and learning process.

3. Is there a significant difference between the teachers' level of utilization in technology integration when grouped according to profile?

Table 4. *Difference in the Teachers' Level of Utilization in Technology Integration by Age*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Fvalue</i>	<i>sig</i>	<i>Decision Ho</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Educational Online Videos	1.729	.170	Accept	Not Significant
Independent Online Learning	5.809	.001	Reject	Significant
Gamified Online Learning	.841	.510	Accept	Not Significant
Interactive Technology	3.493	.019	Reject	Significant
Overall	2.968	.175	Accept	Not Significant

Using ANOVA or F-Test, the difference in the teacher's level of utilization in technology integration by age yielded significant findings in terms of independent online learning and interactive technology. This implied that the respondents differed in their responses regardless of age on how they utilized technology integration in terms of those aspects. On the other hand, there were no significant findings found in terms of educational online videos and gamified online learning. This implied that the respondents revealed similar responses on how they utilized technology integration in those aspects.

In parallel, the findings disclose that teacher's utilization of educational videos and gamified learning in classrooms varies across all age groups. The researcher observed that the daily routine and structure in these classrooms consistently involve the use of YouTube and online videos. Specifically, teachers from Kindergarten to 2nd grade employed these videos daily for motivational and preliminary activities, such as songs and phonological awareness concepts like the Secret Stories of Alphabet. Similarly on gamified online learning, teachers often use it in the classroom for higher engagement. This practice was mandated by the school district to ensure that students master the sounds represented by letters. In addition, teachers regardless of age were well equipped with training in the use of these technologies.

Relevant to the finding was Pattiers' study on Teachers and YouTube in 2021. A total of 1,150 respondents participated in the study aimed at verifying the usage of these platforms from Kindergarten to college. According to the study, elementary teachers utilized videos in the classroom at least one to five times a week. Furthermore, it was concealed that teachers integrated YouTube for motivation, relevance to the lesson objectives, and clarity of the lesson content.

Table 5. *Post Hoc ANOVA Test on the Difference in the Teachers' Level of Utilization in Technology Integration by Age in terms of /Independent Online Learning and Interactive Technology*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Pair of Age</i>	<i>Mean Difference</i>	<i>Sig</i>	<i>Decision Ho</i>	<i>Interpret</i>
Independent Online Learning	31-40 y/o vs. 61-70 y/o	3.07692 *	.009	Reject	Significant
	41-50 y/o vs. 61-70 y/o	3.00000 *	.011	Reject	Significant
	51-60 y/o vs. 61-70 y/o	3.80000 *	.003	Reject	Significant
Interactive Technology	31-40 y/o vs. 61-70 y/o	3.00000 *	.029	Reject	Significant

*. *The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.*

Using a Scheffé Test, the post hoc ANOVA analysis on the difference in the teachers' level of utilization in technology integration in terms of independent online learning yielded significant findings among these pairs of teachers' ages such as 31-40 years old versus 61-70 years old or vice versa; 41-50 years old versus 61-70 years old or vice-versa and 51-60 years old versus 61-70 years old or vice-versa. This implicit varied levels of utilization in technology integration in terms of self-paced/independent online learning. On the other hand, only the pair of 31-40 years old versus 61-70 years old or vice-versa yielded a significant result on the level of utilization of teachers in technology integration in terms of interactive technology. Teachers of different age groups vary in their use of self-paced or independent online learning and Interactive Technology.

In a focus group discussion conducted by the researcher, teachers disclosed that the use of assigning students to perform a task on the computer varies as well as incorporating interactive technologies. Teachers divulged reasons for integrating online independent learning and interactive technology depending on the data result of their class performance. A teacher from the age group of 60 and above said that she utilized independent online learning in Language Arts three times a week and for Math twice a week only since their scores are higher in Math than in Language Arts.

However, based on the group of teachers ages 40 and above, two of them employed a wider range of programs compared to their older counterparts. This variation was confirmed through responses that detailed the independent and interactive online programs used in the classroom during the focus group discussion (Annex A). Additionally, some educators mentioned they are incorporating new platforms that they discovered through training sessions or from colleagues.

From the focus group discussion composed of teachers from different age groups, younger teachers stated the use of at least three different online programs such as Epic, Storyline Online, Spark, Zearn and I station for online self-paced independent programs. Neither

of the respondents mentioned the use of specific interactive technology programs. For younger kids, teachers would assign engaging gamified online programs for enrichment in their independent study time.

In addition, teachers belonging to the middle age group suggested that they use the interactive board primarily to engage learners in the classroom. They use it mainly for engagement and motivation purposes. Teachers in the middle age group use online independent programs and interactive board interchangeably due to training and offers from the school district. Occasionally, school districts send invitations for Professional Development and teachers would have the opportunity to attend.

Similarly, Keržič, D., Danko, M., Zorko, V., and Dečman, M. (2021) revealed in the study that younger teachers assumed to be incorporating technologies and better understand learners. In the data analysis, it showed that younger teachers have different social media accounts and utilize games online which is also the trend for younger students. This is a presumption as to why teachers from younger age groups explore dynamic innovation in using technology in the classroom.

In contrast, Mohd Ismail, Rahida, Arshad, Rozita, and Abas, Zakaria (2018) conferred on the influence of teachers' age on their effectiveness that teachers aged 31 to 40, 41 to 50, and those over 50 years old had significantly higher effectiveness scores compared to teachers aged 21 to 30 years old. This suggests that older teachers tend to be more effective than their younger counterparts. Older teachers appear more willing to embrace new Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) and are better prepared to improve the quality of learning and teaching. Although the study did not specifically address the engagement of learners with teachers' age, it is evident that experienced teachers are more likely to be effective than younger educators.

Table 6. *Differences in the Teachers' Level of Utilization in Technology Integration by Sex*

Variables	Mean		tvalue	sig	Decision Ho	Interpret
	Male	Female				
Educational Online Videos	2.33	3.41	-2.381	.023	Reject	Significant
Independent Online Learning	1.00	3.09	-3.122	.004	Reject	Significant
Gamified Online Learning	1.67	2.66	-1.667	.105	Accept	Not Significant
Interactive Technology	1.00	2.72	-2.399	.022	Reject	Significant
Overall	1.50	2.97	-2.392	.039	Reject	Significant

Using a T-Test of Independent Samples, significant differences were found in the teachers' level of technology integration by sex in terms of educational online videos, self-paced/independent online learning, and interactive technology. This bared that respondents differed in their answers, irrespective of sex, regarding how they utilized technology integration in these aspects. On the other hand, no significant difference was found in terms of gamified online learning, indicating that respondents had similar responses on how they utilized technology integration in this aspect, regardless of sex.

As supported by the respondents' answers during the focus group discussions, female teachers most likely choose a variety of online programs compared to male. Out of 10 participants from the focus group, only one male respondent noted "And if I said to them, you could go here like I made my own. I made my own list of apps, popular stuff on my page, on my classroom page so that they can quickly access it. And I could see what they were going to. They weren't engaging with these E sparks. They would engage with, like, storyline, online story time online (2nd Grade Male Teacher).

Female teachers stated the dynamics of programs used for educational videos, self-paced/independent online learning, and interactive technology. One observation that the researcher could infer was male teachers have a small amount of patience compared to female teachers. This is true when the male teacher noted they were not engaging with Espark. The Espark programs were used by these teachers and female teachers did not specifically mention less engagement from this technology. Instead, female teachers enumerated diverse online independent programs for their classes.

In support of this finding, the article from Hansen and Quintero (2018) asserted that the teaching profession has gradually become more female dominated over the years. Recent statistics show that women make up 76.3 percent of the workforce, an increase from 70.5 percent three decades ago. While this shift might appear minor, it represents a significant imbalance: nearly 200,000 more male teachers would be required today to restore the gender ratio that existed in 1988.

Gebhardt, Thomson, Ainley, and Hillman, (2019) observed that, on average, female teachers reported slightly more experience with using computers for teaching compared to their male counterparts. Despite this, there were no overall differences in the positive or negative views of female and male teachers regarding the use of ICT in education. However, in some countries, female teachers expressed somewhat more positive attitudes towards ICT in education than their male peers. This suggests a potential reason for why female teachers might utilize and employ various technologies in the classroom more frequently than male teachers.

Table 7. *Difference in the Teachers' Level of Utilization in Technology Integration by Years of Teaching Experience*

Variables	Fvalue	sig	Decision Ho	Interpretation
Educational Online Videos	.032	.969	Accept	Not Significant
Independent Online Learning	4.093	.026	Reject	Significant
Gamified Online Learning	.044	.957	Accept	Not Significant
Interactive Technology	.633	.537	Accept	Not Significant

Overall	1.200	.622	Accept	Not Significant
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Using ANOVA or F-Test, the difference in the teacher’s level of utilization in technology integration by years of teaching experience yielded a significant result in terms of self-paced/independent online learning. This implied that the respondents differed in their responses regardless of the years of teaching experience on how they utilized technology integration in terms of this aspect.

On the other hand, there were no significant findings found in terms of educational online videos, gamified online learning, and interactive technology. This implied that the respondents revealed similar responses on how they utilized technology integration in those aspects.

The school district offers continuous training on modern technologies throughout the year. Regardless of tenure, all teachers, including new and experienced ones, receive professional training and mentoring on the integration of technology into their teaching practices. This comprehensive training likely accounts for the absence of significant differences in most variables, except for the integration of online learning. As noted in previous discussions, teachers utilize online learning tools based on the specific needs and data reports from their classes.

Carstens (2021) discussed the immediate impact of educational technology, asserting the potential to enhance learning and retention. However, the speed of these results can be observed depending on various factors, including educational objectives, technological choices, the socioeconomic demographics of the school and its students, and the effective implementation and utilization of new equipment within the organization. This suggests that the number of years of teaching experience does not significantly affect the utilization of technology in the classroom. Consequently, regardless of whether teachers are new or experienced, their ability to integrate technology effectively is influenced more by these external factors than by their teaching tenure.

Table 8. *Post Hoc ANOVA Test on the Difference in the Teachers’ Level of Utilization in Technology Integration by Teaching Experience in terms of Independent Online Learning*

Variables	Pair of Years of Teaching Experience	Mean Difference	sig	Decision Ho	Interpret
Self- Paced/Independent Online Learning	1-5 years vs. 11-15 years	-1.33333 *	.030	Reject	Significant

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Using a Sheffe Test, the post hoc ANOVA analysis on the difference in the teachers’ level of utilization in technology integration in terms of selfpaced/independent online learning yielded a significant result between 1- 5 years and 11-15 years. This implied a varied level of utilization in technology integration in terms of this aspect.

Supporting the data mentioned was evidence from scripts generated during focus group discussions. These discussions highlighted that younger teachers are currently in the exploratory phase of integrating technology to best serve their learners. In contrast, teachers with over 10 years of experience have honed their skills in identifying which types of technology and programs are most effective for their students. Experienced teachers tend to utilize independent learning platforms more frequently than their less experienced counterparts, likely because they understand the effectiveness of these technologies and have mastered the programs, including their strengths and weaknesses. New teachers, meanwhile, are often in the initial stages of discovering and learning about these technologies, possibly seeking guidance from more experienced peers.

Ladd (2013) coined that experienced teachers consistently outperform their less experienced counterparts in leveraging student achievement across elementary, middle, and high schools. This higher effectiveness remains significant even when accounting for the fact that experienced teachers often work in more advantaged environments. According to research conducted in North Carolina in 2013, teachers generally show substantial improvement in their initial years, with math teachers in middle school continuing to enhance their ability to raise test scores for up to 15 years, becoming approximately twice as effective as those with only two years of experience. While the gains for middle school English teachers are less pronounced, they still follow a similar upward trajectory. Notably, even teachers with over two decades of experience continue to be more effective than they were at the beginning of their careers.

Table 9. *Difference in the Teachers’ Level of Utilization in Technology Integration by Highest Educational Attainment*

Variables	Fvalue	sig	Decision Ho	Interpretation
Educational Online Videos	.674	.616	Accept	Not Significant
Independent Online Learning	1.436	.246	Accept	Not Significant
Gamified Online Learning	.515	.725	Accept	Not Significant
Interactive Technology	.833	.515	Accept	Not Significant
Overall	.864	.526	Accept	Not Significant

Using ANOVA or F-Test, the difference in the teachers’ level of utilization in technology integration by highest educational attainment yielded no significant findings in terms of educational online videos, independent online learning, gamified online learning, and

interactive technology. This affirmed that irrespective of the highest educational attainment of teachers, their levels of utilization in technology integration were the same in terms of those aspects. The null hypothesis was accepted at a 5% level of significance.

Researchers have observed over the past five years that many teachers in the United States often exhibit a reluctance to pursue graduate studies. This hesitation can be attributed to several factors. Firstly, the perceived financial burden of graduate education is a significant deterrent. Secondly, the time commitment required for advanced studies presents a substantial challenge for many educators. Thirdly, many teachers express satisfaction with the training and professional development opportunities currently available to them. Additionally, some teachers are apprehensive about the increased responsibilities that often accompany advanced degrees and higher qualifications.

In support, Winter, Costello, O'Brien, and Hickey, (2021) noted that the educational adjustments necessitated by Covid-19 have significantly heightened educators' dependence on technology. Respondents have adapted by using various digital platforms like Zoom, Class Dojo, YouTube, and PowerPoint for teaching. The shift to technology has been essential for continuing education, especially for creating and delivering content remotely. Students have generally adapted well to using technology for schoolwork, which may influence future educational practices such as more frequent online homework assignments. While some educators have successfully maintained engagement and learning levels despite school closures, others expressed a need for further training to enhance their confidence and skills in using online learning platforms. Overall, responses varied with some teachers feeling more confident with remote teaching tools like Google Classroom and Zoom, whereas others still feel the need to improve their ability to engage students through varied and interactive content delivery.

4. What is the level of engagement of learner-respondents using applied technology in the classroom in terms of educational online videos, independent online learning, gamified online learning, and interactive technology?

Table 10. *Level of Engagement of Learner-Respondents Using Applied Technology in the Classroom in terms of Educational Online Videos*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Learners are engaged using educational multimedia videos in presenting a lesson	3.06	0.97	Often
Learners easily follow instructions from teacher in assigning work using multimedia technology	2.54	1.09	Often
Learner's interest is high using multimedia technology	2.89	1.05	Often
Online educational reading programs engaged learners	2.80	1.11	Often
Behavior and disruption occur during presentation of online educational videos	1.51	0.89	Never
Composite	2.56	1.02	Often

Scale: 4.00-3.26=Always; 3.25-2.51= Often; 2.50-1.76=Sometimes; 1.75-1.00=Never

In terms of educational online videos, the level of engagement of learner respondents using an applied technology in the classroom yielded a composite mean score of 2.56 with a 1.02 corresponding standard deviation. This made known that learners were very engaged in educational online videos in the classroom. Of all the indicators, the highest mean score was evident when using educational multimedia videos online when teachers were presenting their lessons. This indicator was often experienced by the learners in the classroom.

Similarly, in the school setting where the researcher conducted the study, the widely used platform YouTube is integrated into daily classroom activities for various educational purposes. For younger students, YouTube is primarily utilized to provide motivation, introduce new concepts, aid in content retention, and enhance phonemic awareness. Additionally, it is employed during read-aloud sessions and storytelling activities, thereby enriching the learning experience for these students. For older students, YouTube serves as a valuable resource for supplementing lesson content with educational videos, providing visual and auditory reinforcement of complex concepts, and offering diverse perspectives on various subjects. Teachers also utilize YouTube to demonstrate real-world applications of theoretical concepts, conduct virtual field trips, and facilitate flipped classroom models, where students watch instructional videos at home and participates in hands-on activities during class. This diverse use of YouTube in the classroom highlights its versatility as an educational tool that accommodates various learning styles and needs.

Likewise, Keddie, J. (2014) described the digital area in which learners primarily relate to the presentation of lessons, such as storytelling with the aid of videos. Online educational sources such as "YouTube" are defined as the third most trafficked sites on the Internet as millions of people utilize the platform, and educators use it for different purposes.

As such, findings like the data above indicate that learners' engagement can vary based on the content of the video presented. One teacher from the focus group discussion mentioned that kids would be most likely to engage depending on their interests the reason why teachers marked "sometimes" when it comes to learners' engagement in using educational videos.

Vagin, A. (2015) discussed how online videos were utilized in teaching to promote social learning, specifically for kids with specific learning disabilities. She utilizes videos to aid students with learning disabilities to understand their feelings and emotions. Since students with autism mainly engage using videos and images, it has served as a tool and aid for instruction. This tool also served as the bridge to connect and understand learners' perspectives using images and videos.

The researcher noticed that teachers often pause and stop videos to allow students to follow along, particularly when asking them to

perform tasks such as guided drawing or answering comprehension questions related to the story. Additionally, teachers could play, pause, and revisit key moments in the video to highlight important aspects of the lesson. This approach is particularly beneficial for students who may struggle to keep up. However, for faster learners, this method can lead to boredom, potentially resulting in behavioral issues in the classroom.

Mandar's (2015) study on Teacher Readiness in Multimedia Instruction revealed that students in grades 4 to 6 are highly interested in the classroom when multimedia is used. This level of interest in reference to engagement showed that online videos are indeed engaging for students. As a result, training for teachers was conducted to address specific challenges for targeted teachers' skill in multimedia instruction.

Conversely, teachers have observed certain behaviors in the classroom when using educational videos. For instance, a teacher reported a case where a child with Autism frequently eloped during video sessions. The researcher, who also taught the child, gathered data and monitored the situation during these times. Utilizing the ABC (Antecedent, Behavior, Consequence) method, the case manager helped the teacher address this behavior. A one-week observation revealed that the sound from the television triggered the child's sensory sensitivities, prompting elopement.

Therefore, the integration of technology in the classroom can either alleviate or exacerbate student stress and anxiety, depending on how it is implemented. Just as adverse lighting conditions can heighten a child's discomfort, leading to negative behavioral responses, or inadequately supported technological interventions can increase stress and anxiety among students and those with special needs. For instance, if the technology is not user-friendly or if students do not receive sufficient guidance and support in using it, they may feel overwhelmed and frustrated.

Correspondingly, when technology is thoughtfully integrated, with attention to the specific needs and comfort levels of students, it can enhance the learning environment, reduce anxiety, and foster a more engaging and supportive educational experience. This highlights the importance of careful consideration and planning in the deployment of technological tools in the classroom to ensure they contribute positively to the learning environment.

Table 11. *Level of Engagement of Learner-Respondents Using Applied Technology in the Classroom in terms of Independent Online Learning*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Learners are engaged to perform independent online programs	2.57	1.04	Often
Learners take accountability of their classwork using technology.	2.49	1.15	Sometimes
Independent online interventions are helpful for my students.	2.46	1.17	Sometimes
Behaviors occursn during selfpaced learning.	1.49	0.82	Never
Artificial Intelligence (AI) helps to choose intervention for independent online programs	1.20	1.18	Never
Composite	2.04	1.07	Sometimes

In terms of independent online learning, the level of engagement of learner respondents using an applied technology in the classroom yielded a composite mean score of 2.04 with a 1.07 corresponding standard deviation. Specifically, the highest mean score was evident by learner engagement when they performed independent online programs. Of all the indicators, the lowest mean score was apparent using artificial intelligence (AI) as the tool to assign intervention used by the learners in the classroom.

From the focus group discussion, participants revealed that they use chrome books daily for enrichment and intervention activities. Students are required to complete computer-based tasks every day. The self-paced and independent programs depend on the assignments given by the teacher. Learners can choose from programs that have been approved and saved by the teachers. The online programs assigned vary in difficulty, depending on the students' performance on each set of tasks. Kindergarten and 1st-grade teachers frequently use Storyline Online and Epic Reading, as many of the students are beginning readers.

On the other hand, teachers mentioned the use of Istation at least three times a week. One teacher from kindergarten notes "I use I station at least three times a week for Reading and two times a week for Math, since our scores are higher in Math"

The respondents' statements suggest that the implementation of these interventions was contingent upon the data on class performance. Furthermore, teachers were more likely to employ these strategies when it was necessary for students to spend time familiarizing themselves with the platform's structure. This approach was also used to train students to remain engaged for a specific duration before transitioning to another online program of their interest.

Fullan (2011) noted that there is sometimes a convergence of independent but related variables in the use of technology in teaching, which can lead to significant advancements in societal learning. He stated, "We are at the beginning of a potentially powerful alignment of factors that could revolutionize education. Fullan emphasized that innovative and effective teaching practices support student-centered pedagogy by which includes five key components: personalization/individualization, collaboration, student self-regulation, knowledge-building, and skilled communication. He also highlighted that information and communication technology (ICT) plays a critical role in enhancing and extending learning beyond the classroom particularly in areas such as problem-solving and innovation. These practices, he asserted, positively influence students' 21st-century learning skills.

According to Hillman, D., Schudy, R., and Temkin, A. (2022), "Asynchronous instruction allows educators to utilize a wider range of technology and teaching methods." They explained that this type of instruction enables students to complete tasks and work at their own pace, allowing teachers to tailor instruction based on the most effective learning methods for each student.

Table 12. *Level of Engagement of Learner-Respondents Using Applied Technology in the Classroom in terms of Gamified Online Learning*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Learners are active in playing educational online games	3.20	0.96	Always
Learners are engaged in doing classwork via online games	2.91	1.15	Always
Behavior and disruption occur to learners who are using educational games online	1.69	0.96	Sometimes
Learners are struggling to perform games on their computer	1.86	1.09	Sometimes
AI educational programs are helpful in designing engaging lessons for gamified learning	1.20	1.18	Never
Composite	2.20	1.07	Sometimes

In terms of gamified online learning, the level of engagement of learner respondents using an applied technology in the classroom yielded a composite mean score of 2.20 with a corresponding standard deviation of 1.07. This implied that learners were sometimes engaged in gamified online learning in the classroom. Of all the indicators, the highest mean score was evident by the attitude of learners who are mostly active when they play educational online games. This was followed by the characteristics of learners who are mostly engaged in doing educational online games. Among other indicators, the lowest mean score was apparent using AI tools to set programs designed for online gamified learning.

Educational online games are occasionally integrated into teaching strategies to enhance student engagement. Teachers have observed that students often exhibit increased enthusiasm, particularly when they see their names on leaderboards. However, the use of such games is not consistent; teachers' decisions to incorporate them depend significantly on the classroom's overall mood and dynamics. During a focus group discussion, one teacher noted that the incorporation of online games varies based on the classroom environment at any given time. Despite this variability, it is generally agreed that students derive enjoyment from the integration of online games into their learning experiences. This positive reception underscores the potential of gamification as a valuable tool in fostering an engaging and interactive educational environment.

Likewise, gamification has become increasingly popular in education due to its many benefits. One major advantage is that it creates a learning environment that is multi-sensory, active, and hands-on. This approach enables students to participate in experiential learning, where they can enhance their decision-making and problem-solving skills within a dynamic environment (Adachi & Willoughby, 2013).

Additionally, educational games provide immediate feedback, unlike traditional assessment methods such as tests and exams, which often involve delayed feedback. This instant feedback helps students understand and correct their mistakes in real-time. Moreover, gamification breaks down barriers of time and place, as students can use portable devices to learn anytime and anywhere. This flexibility makes it easier for students to grasp and remember difficult subjects (Hanus and Fox, 2015).

Despite extensive research supporting the benefits of gamification, it does not always receive unanimous advocacy due to mixed results (Hanus and Fox, 2015). As teachers assign online games to students, behavior can sometimes occur because learners are struggling to perform games. Teachers mentioned that learners with special needs needed additional support when introduced to online games.

Table 13. *Level of Engagement of Learner-Respondents Using Applied Technology in the Classroom in terms of Interactive Technology*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Learners are engaged using Interactive technology in the classroom for gaming and instruction	3.11	0.96	Often
Learners collaborate interactively using interactive technology	2.46	1.20	Often
Learners participate actively when I use online interactive games.	2.91	1.09	Often
Learners are motivated using interactive activity on their computer	2.89	1.05	Often
Behavior occurs during interactive technology time.	1.60	0.85	Never
Composite	2.60	1.03	Often

Regarding interactive technology, learner respondents reported a composite mean score of 2.60 with a standard deviation of 1.03, indicating a high level of engagement with interactive technology in the classroom. Among the indicators, the highest mean score was observed for learners' engagement when using interactive technology for activities such as gaming or instruction. Conversely, the lowest mean score was related to behaviors observed during interactive technology use.

Comparatively, first-grade teachers noted during the Focus Group Discussion (FGD) that they use Google Classroom to send activities and homework. "I think they are more engaged when we use technology, but they have their favorite things," the teacher refers to applications that students enjoy, such as "Prodigy." Prodigy is an online interactive game where learners can interact live with their

classmates. They earn points by answering questions based on the content, and once they pass, they earn badges, which adds to their motivation. Some teachers reported that learners enjoyed engaging with interactive online games such as Boddle and Prodigy. In these platforms, teachers could customize the skill level based on individual student needs, allowing students to master specific skills through gameplay. However, a noted drawback of this approach is that some learners might become so absorbed in the activity that they exceed the allotted time for the game.

Incorporating interactive whiteboards and using online interactive technology significantly engages learners based on the teacher's perception from the focus group discussion. This approach transforms the teacher's role into that of a facilitator, while students take accountability and ownership of their learning, thereby developing critical thinking and collaboration skills. However, the effectiveness of this method is contingent upon the nature of the assigned tasks and the content of the lesson.

In addition, Steel, G. (2020) introduced the book "Google Classroom: A Complete Step-by-Step Guide to Become a Distance Learning Expert." He developed the book to support teachers in maximizing teaching using Google in Education during the Pandemic. Google for Education is a free tool that allows teachers and students to work collaboratively. Google Drive is an online storage that enables users to store files with limited space shared by students. Students can work on the same document and interact with it all simultaneously or at their own pace. Teachers can assign work and act as facilitators. Aside from Google Docs, Google Classroom was the primary classroom during the Pandemic. Lessons, tasks, homework, and quizzes are all integrated into a platform. As the need for live lessons arose, Google Classroom added an instant button to allow students to have a live conference with their teachers. This interactive feature allows for live lessons and an interactive approach. To add, students used Google Chats to send and exchange conversations, including polls for survey questions to promote student engagement.

Table 14. *Overall Level of Engagement of Learner-Respondents Using Applied Technology in the Classroom*

Variables	Mean	Composite		Rank
		SD	Description	
Educational Online Videos	2.56	1.02	Often	2
Independent Online Learning	2.04	1.07	Sometimes	4
Gamified Online Learning	2.20	1.07	Sometimes	3
Interactive Technology	2.60	1.03	Often	1
Overall	2.31	1.06	Sometimes	--

Of all the variables of the level of engagement of learners using applied technology in the classroom, the one on the top rank was apparent by interactive technology followed by educational videos, gamified online, and independent online learning. Overall, the above findings revealed that the engagement of learners using applied technology was sometimes manifested in the classroom.

The researcher observed various methods of integrating interactive technology in the classroom. For younger students in Kindergarten, teachers frequently employ technology for classroom activities, games, and task demonstrations. In 1st grade, tools such as Google Slides enable students to interact and work on computers while teachers provide immediate feedback. Accordingly, interactive platforms that combine videos, activities, and games within a single application can maximize the use of technology. These platforms are particularly effective in engaging students with special needs, though some students may initially face difficulties. However, with proper training and acclimatization, the use of interactive platforms can streamline lesson delivery, maximize instructional time, and minimize potential behavioral issues in the classroom.

Martin (2021) describes interactive learning as a teaching method that prioritizes student participation and engagement. This approach motivates learners to participate in hands-on activities, collaborate in groups, and use technology to complete their classwork. The goal of interactive learning is to quickly and effectively capture students' attention ensuring they stay engaged in the learning process.

When adopting this approach, it is crucial to shift some authority from the teacher to the students, focusing on developing their problem-solving, collaboration, and creativity skills. This transition allows students to take a more active role in their learning, creating a more engaging and skill-oriented educational environment.

The data indicates that interactive learning is highly effective in promoting classroom engagement. Learners become more active participants rather than passive listeners. In this method, the teacher's role evolves from being the main source of information to acting as a facilitator. This change empowers students to take control of their learning, engage more deeply with the material, and collaborate effectively with peers. The teacher's role is to guide and support, encouraging the development of critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and creativity. This active involvement fosters a dynamic and engaging learning environment, ultimately enhancing the overall educational experience.

Researchers' observations indicate that the use of educational videos by teachers is consistent, as this tool effectively demonstrates and expands learning concepts, particularly for young learners. Educational videos serve as an invaluable aid in the classroom, providing students with the opportunity to comprehend concepts more meaningfully through the integration of audiovisual elements and actual footage of real-world phenomena.

On the other hand, in terms of utilization and engagement using online videos in the classroom, Vagin, A. (2015) discussed how online

videos were utilized in teaching to promote social learning, specifically for kids with specific learning disabilities. She utilizes videos to aid students with learning disabilities to understand their feelings and emotions. Since students with autism mainly engage using videos and images, it has served as a tool and aid for instruction. This tool also served as the bridge to connect and understand learners' perspectives using images and videos.

Biard et al., (2017) suggested that learners should be given opportunities for system-determined pauses at points where viewers likely to stop the videos themselves. Therefore, it is important to examine learners' reasons for pausing videos in a natural viewing context to identify these key points. This is evident as teachers frequently use videos in the classroom to explain concepts more effectively. The ability to pause the video and give students time to think and observe visual images significantly contributes to increased learning engagement.

Moving forward to online gamified learning, data demonstrated that learners were slightly engaged in this mode of learning. Several factors influence this level of engagement, including the age and developmental stage of the learners. Kindergarten to 2nd grade students is still in the process of developing their reading and comprehension skills, which can affect their ability to fully participate in gamified learning activities.

However, second-grade teachers often use gamified learning for intervention purposes, as many of their students have reached a level where they can read and follow instructions. This targeted use helps address specific learning needs and enhances engagement among students who are ready for such interactive methods. The overall effectiveness of gamified learning can thus vary significantly based on the readiness and developmental stage of the learners.

Rodrigo et al. (2020) conducted a study on the effect of gamification on learning based on characteristics and personality of learners. It was revealed how different personality traits affect the engagement and performance of students using a gamified learning approach. Introverted students, regardless of whether they were in the control or experimental group, showed higher engagement. They earned more points, and badges, and logged in more frequently than their extroverted peers. Moreover, Introverted students using the gamified system also showed a statistically significant improvement in accuracy. This means that the gamified approach not only engaged introverted students more but also helped them perform better in terms of accuracy.

This study's findings contradict previous research, which primarily focused on undergraduate students. The current research, however, involved younger learners, highlighting different engagement levels. Teachers reported that students with special needs showed low engagement with gamified learning tools. According to the transcription, "they are not engaged," suggesting that the level of difficulty might be too challenging for learners with special needs. This indicates that while gamification can be beneficial, its effectiveness may vary significantly based on the student's age, developmental stage, and individual needs.

Finally, last from rank exposed that independent online learning showed slight engagement based on teachers' perspectives.

Since the use of online independent learning is mandated by the school district, teachers consistently incorporate it into their classrooms, with particular emphasis on the use of Istation. However, this frequent use may lead to student boredom over time. Students with special needs, in particular, struggle to maintain focus on this platform as the level of difficulty increases. To address this issue, teachers often collaborate with resource teachers to provide additional support to these students when they login to the program. This challenge is not limited to students with special needs; younger children in general sometimes find the platform less engaging.

Moreover, the repetitive nature of daily usage can diminish students' initial enthusiasm, potentially impacting their overall motivation and learning outcomes. Teachers have noted that while Istation offers valuable content and exercises, its effectiveness is sometimes undermined by a lack of variety and interactive elements that captivate young learners. To mitigate these issues, some educators supplement Istation with other interactive and diverse educational tools to maintain student interest and engagement. Additionally, professional development sessions focus on equipping teachers with strategies to better integrate Istation with other classroom activities, ensuring a balanced and stimulating learning environment for all students. Despite these efforts, it remains crucial to continually assess and adapt the use of online learning platforms to meet the evolving needs and preferences of students, particularly those requiring special education services.

Supporting the findings were Li, An, N., Deng, L., and Zeng, S. (2024) coined the need of assistance for a child when doing online independent learning. In this study, a first-grade child with intellectual disability was consistently provided with an assistant during reading intervention through an independent online program. The results of this study indicated that students with intellectual disabilities (ID) showed improved early reading skills through the family member-assisted online early reading intervention program.

While the findings are preliminary, they are promising and suggest that even first graders with ID can benefit from online learning. This is particularly important during periods of mass school closures due to pandemics. Crucially, the assistance of family members is essential to the success of this online intervention program. It also helps address inattentive behaviors in students with ID during online learning.

5. Is there a significant difference in learners' engagement using applied technology in the classroom when grouped according to profile of teachers?

Table 15. *Difference in the Learners' Engagement Using Applied Technology in the Classroom by Teachers' Age*

Variables	Fvalue	Sig	Decision Ho	Interpretation
Educational Online Videos	3.929	.011	Reject	Significant
Independent Online Learning	1.728	.170	Accept	Not Significant
Gamified Online Learning	4.887	.004	Reject	Significant
Interactive Technology	2.726	.051	Reject	Significant
Overall	3.317	.059	Accept	Not Significant

Using ANOVA or F-Test, the difference in the learners' engagement using applied technology in the classroom by teacher's age yielded significant findings in terms of educational online videos, gamified online learning, and interactive technology. This implied that the respondents differed in their responses regardless of age on how they viewed learners' engagement using applied technology in the classroom in terms of those aspects. On the other hand, there was no significant result found in terms of independent online learning. This implied that the respondents revealed similar responses on how they viewed learners' engagement using applied technology in the classroom in terms of this aspect.

The results indicated that learner engagement varies depending on the age group of teachers when utilizing online videos and gamified online learning. This suggests that some students may be less likely to participate in tasks when instructed by either younger or older teachers. Younger teachers might bring more familiarity and enthusiasm towards integrating modern technologies, potentially engaging tech-savvy students more effectively. Conversely, older teachers might bring a wealth of experience and a more structured approach, which could resonate better with students who prefer traditional methods.

Dobo (2015) released an article about the "myth" of younger teachers who are "tech-savvy". Accordingly, teachers who typically have more classroom experience are more confident in their ability to use the extensive data provided by digital learning tools. In contrast, younger teachers feel less prepared. Additionally, the survey from the Software and Information Industry Association, presented at a recent conference, reveals that teachers of all ages generally feel inadequately prepared to effectively integrate technology into teaching and learning.

Table 16. *Post Hoc ANOVA Test on the Difference in the Learners' Engagement Using Applied Technology in the Classroom by Teachers' Age in terms of Educational Online Videos, Gamified Online Learning and Interactive Technology*

Variables	Pair of Age	Mean Difference	sig	Decision Ho	Interpret
Educational Online Videos	31-40 y/o vs 61-70 y/o	1.45192*	.046	Reject	Significant
	31-40 y/o vs 61-70 y/o	1.50000*	.019	Reject	Significant
Gamified Online Learning	41-50 y/o vs 61-70 y/o	1.77692*	.004	Reject	Significant
	51-60 y/o vs 61-70 y/o	1.54000*	.033	Reject	Significant
	61-70 y/o				

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Using a Scheffé Test, the post hoc ANOVA analysis on the difference in the learners' engagement using applied technology in the classroom by teacher's age in terms of educational online videos yielded a significant result between 31-40 years old versus 61-70 years old or vice-versa. Furthermore, the gamified online learning disclosed that significant findings were found in the following pairs of ages such as 31-40 years old versus 61-70 years; 41-50 years old versus 61-70 years old or vice-versa and 51-60 years old versus 61-70 years old or vice-versa. This inferred varied levels of utilization in technology integration in terms of gamified online learning.

This phenomenon is particularly evident when teachers refer students with special needs to resource teachers for scaffolding and breaking down instructions in small group intervention services. Teachers, regardless of their age group, dedicate significant time to scaffolding lessons for learners with slower comprehension. Younger teachers may employ more contemporary, interactive methods for scaffolding, while older teachers might utilize established, traditional techniques.

Additionally, teachers may send some students to the resource room when gamified tasks prove challenging for those with special needs. These accommodations are often documented in students' files for teachers to reference and incorporate into their instructional strategies. This practice ensures that all students receive the necessary support and aligns with survey responses regarding instructional accommodations.

Overall, this highlights the importance of tailored instructional strategies that consider the diverse needs of students and the varying strengths that different age groups of educators bring to the classroom. Effective professional development and collaborative teaching approaches can help bridge these differences, ensuring all students benefit from the strengths of both younger and older teachers.

An article from learn.org (2024) revealed the average age of educators significantly impacts various aspects of education, such as technology utilization in terms of age using gamified learning. Younger educators tend to incorporate cutting-edge technologies and

innovative pedagogies, while older educators might prefer more traditional approaches. This age diversity creates opportunities for mentoring, which enhances professional growth.

Perhaps this had a contributing factor to the findings of the study which manifested that teacher's utilization of technology in educational video, gamified online learning, and interactive learning varies. To add, both K-12 and higher education educators emphasize the importance of professional development to improve their use of student data. This indicates a strong demand for more training programs to help teachers effectively leverage data in their teaching practices.

In contrast, Liberman (2017) recommends that educators discard the belief that students' technological abilities surpass their own and instead focus on collaborative technology use in teaching. Wendy Drexler of Johns Hopkins University and Katie Davis of the University of Washington agree with the need for professional development but question the relevance of the digital native concept. Davis notes that while young people are familiar with technology, they lack the discernment skills that come with maturity.

Table 17. *Difference in the Learners' Engagement Using Applied Technology in the Classroom by Teachers' Sex*

Variables	Mean		tvalue	Sig	Decision Ho	Interpretation
	Male	Female				
Educational Online Videos	1.67	2.55	-2.342	.025	Reject	Significant
Independent Online Learning	1.33	2.24	-2.047	.049	Reject	Significant
Gamified Online Learning	1.47	2.30	-1.114	.378	Accept	Not Significant
Interactive Technology	1.62	2.43	-1.387	.296	Accept	Not Significant
Overall	1.52	2.38	-1.723	.187	Accept	Not Significant

Using a T-Test of Independent Samples, significant differences were found in learners' engagement with applied technology in the classroom based on the teacher's sex, specifically in the areas of educational online videos and independent online learning. This suggests that respondents had different perceptions, regardless of sex, regarding learners' engagement with applied technology in these areas. However, no significant differences were found in perceptions related to gamified online learning and interactive technology, indicating that respondents had similar views on learners' engagement with these types of technology, regardless of sex.

These findings suggest that the perceived needs of learners and the authoritative role of teachers in incorporating technology in the classroom may contribute to differences in engagement. Many respondents were female teachers, who may have more experience and confidence in effectively integrating technology. In contrast, the smaller number of male teachers, who are relatively new to the field, might still be exploring various technologies in their teaching practices.

The higher engagement observed with female teachers could be attributed to their familiarity and proficiency with technological tools, as well as their ability to tailor these tools to meet students' needs. Female teachers' extensive use of technology might create more interactive and engaging learning environments, particularly for male students who may respond well to dynamic and varied instructional methods facilitated by technology.

Additionally, another factor to consider is the teachers' attitudes and behaviors toward learners and how effectively they engage students in using applied technology. Gebhardt, Thomson, Ainley, and Hillman (2019) noted that female teachers generally placed greater emphasis on teaching ICT skills to students compared to their male counterparts. This observation aligns with the statement made by a male teacher during an interview: "I made my own list of apps, popular stuff on my page, on my classroom page so that they can quickly access it. And I could see what they were going to. They weren't engaging with these Espark. They would engage with, like, storyline, online story time online."

This indicated that the male teacher focused on technology that would more directly engage his learners and did not explore a broader range of tools. Consequently, his classroom page offered limited options for students.

Conversely, many female teachers reported using a variety of programs to enhance student engagement, indicating a more extensive and exploratory approach to integrating technology in their teaching practices.

Table 18. *Difference in the Learners' Engagement Using Applied Technology in the Classroom by Teachers' Years of Teaching*

Variables	Fvalue	Sig	Decision Ho	Interpretation
Educational Online Videos	.236	.791	Accept	Not Significant
Independent Online Learning	2.662	.085	Accept	Not Significant
Gamified Online Learning	.376	.689	Accept	Not Significant
Interactive Technology	.215	.808	Accept	Not Significant
Overall	.872	.593	Accept	Not Significant

Using ANOVA or F-Test, the difference in the learners' engagement using applied technology in the classroom by teacher's years of teaching yielded no significant findings in terms of educational online videos, independent online learning, gamified online learning, and interactive technology. This implied that irrespective of the years of teaching experience of teachers, the levels of learners' engagement using applied technology in the classroom were the same in terms of those aspects. The null hypothesis was accepted at a

5% level of significance.

These findings offered that effectiveness of applied technology in engaging learners is not dependent on how long teachers have been in the profession. Both rookies and veteran teachers seem to achieve similar levels of student engagement when using educational online videos, facilitating independent online learning, implementing gamified online learning, and integrating interactive technology.

Possible reasons to contribute could be modern educational technologies are designed to be user-friendly and accessible to teachers with varying levels of experience. This design might help level the playing field, ensuring that both new and experienced teachers can effectively engage students.

Bryant and Sarakatsannis (2016) reported that US schools allocate \$18 billion annually for teacher professional development which is twice the amount spent on digital and print instructional materials. This highlights the critical importance of professional development. Many schools invest significantly in continuous training for their teachers, focusing on the latest technological tools and methods. This continuous education helps bridge any gaps that might otherwise result from differences in teaching experience.

Table 19. *Difference in the Learners' Engagement Using Applied Technology in the Classroom by Teachers' Highest Educational Attainment*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Fvalue</i>	<i>Sig</i>	<i>Decision Ho</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Educational Online Videos	.295	.879	Accept	Not Significant
Independent Online Learning	.468	.759	Accept	Not Significant
Gamified Online Learning	1.531	.218	Accept	Not Significant
Interactive Technology	1.203	.330	Accept	Not Significant
Overall	.874	.547	Accept	Not Significant

Using ANOVA or F-Test, the difference in the learners' engagement using applied technology in the classroom by teacher's highest educational attainment yielded no significant findings in terms of educational online videos, or independent online learning.

Data indicated that teachers' highest educational attainment did not significantly impact their use of applied technology in the classroom. With an overall significance level of .874, the null hypothesis was accepted, suggesting no difference based on educational attainment. This implies that teachers holding a bachelor's degree utilized technology in the same manner as those with graduate degrees.

Possible reasons for the lack of significant differences in learner engagement based on teachers' highest educational attainment may include factors such as professional development, training, collaboration with peers, and the influence of social media. In school districts across the United States, training and professional development opportunities are widely accessible to all teachers, often offered at no cost. Furthermore, teachers are generally compensated for attending these training sessions, providing an incentive for ongoing professional growth.

These professional development opportunities keep teachers abreast of the latest technological advancements that can be incorporated into the classroom. Currently, many training programs emphasize artificial intelligence, interactive technology, and content creation, all of which are designed to enhance student engagement.

Moreover, the collaborative nature of professional development sessions fosters an environment where teachers can share best practices and innovative strategies, further enriching their technological repertoire. Social media also plays a significant role by providing a platform for teachers to exchange ideas and resources globally. These factors collectively contribute to the ability of teachers, regardless of their educational attainment as indicated by the findings, to effectively integrate a diverse range of technologies into their instructional practices.

Supporting this, the study by MÜCAHİT AYDOĞMUŞ, EDİP TUT, YILDIRAY KARADAĞ' (2023) revealed that teachers utilized social media in various ways both inside and outside the classroom. They employed social media for self-improvement and lesson preparation capturing students' attention at the start of lessons, clarifying topics during lessons, reinforcing learning outside class, monitoring student progress, and conducting assessments and evaluations.

7. What challenges do teachers encounter in integrating technology in the classroom?

Table 20. *Overall Problems Encountered in Utilizing Applied Technology*

<i>Category</i>	<i>No. of Related Responses</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Digital Literacy	18	1
Technical Concern	7	2
No Problems encountered	3	3
Professional Development	1	4
Total Responses	29	
	YES	NO
Do you have a specific tool to measure learner engagement in the classroom to help you determine	3	22

which approach is most likely to engage your learners during instruction? Write NO if you do not have one, and If YES, please write down the specific tool.

Twenty-nine teacher respondents willingly shared the challenges they face in integrating technology into their classrooms. Among these responses, eighteen (18) emphasized the necessity for enhancing learners' digital literacy skills, followed by concerns related to technical issues and the need for professional development. Additionally, respondents highlighted barriers such as inadequate infrastructure, limited access to resources, and insufficient time to effectively implement technological tools. Notably, when queried about the technology assessment tools they employ, 88% indicated that they do not utilize any such tools, pointing to a significant gap in the evaluation of technological integration within educational practices. This lack of assessment tools underscores the need for more comprehensive support and training for educators in the effective use of technology in the classroom. Integrating various technologies into the classroom has become increasingly essential in modern education, offering numerous benefits such as enhanced engagement, personalized learning, and access to a wealth of resources.

However, despite these advantages, teachers face a myriad of challenges when attempting to incorporate technology into their teaching practices. These obstacles can significantly impact the effectiveness of technology integration and ultimately influence student outcomes.

Responses from participants of the survey were analyzed based on the frequency and content of answers. The following categories were grouped according to the occurrence of relevance to the topic.

Sample responses taken from the respondents were:

1. Students are often reluctant to independently explore new concepts or activities.
2. Excessive screen time is a concern for some students, particularly those who are low functioning. While they frequently prefer to use their Chromebooks, it is essential to balance technological use with other instructional methods that promote hands-on learning, social interaction, and physical movement.
3. When introducing a new platform to students, careful consideration of their needs and capabilities is necessary.
4. Programs designed to be user-friendly for younger children are essential in fostering engagement.
5. Students who lack exposure to technology and face academic challenges often struggle to engage effectively.
6. Identifying programs that span three different grade levels while aligning precisely with each student's unique learning needs is a significant challenge.
7. Many students prefer to play non-educational games.
8. The need to teach students how to access and use technology and applications often results in a loss of instructional time.
9. Maintaining student focus and managing behavior are primary challenges.
10. Children often prefer one-on-one attention and group instruction.
11. Addressing the needs of students with sensory and behavioral issues while considering net neutrality is important.
12. Finding engaging and appropriate grade-level videos and activities can be difficult.
13. Some students either exclusively interact with technology or become so fatigued by it that they prefer traditional pen-and-paper methods. It is challenging to maintain their attention when they are accustomed to being constantly entertained by technology.
14. Finding appropriate technological resources that facilitate student growth rather than simply providing entertainment is crucial.
15. Some students explore inappropriate websites, which is a concern.
16. Teaching the new rules of games or how to use technology effectively requires considerable time.
17. Students do not enjoy the NM Ped-chosen program for reading and math and struggle to stay focused while using it. However, they respond positively to other programs such as Education.com and Teach Your Monster to Read, where they become active learners.
18. One student frequently pulls the wires and cables of the television, which is mounted above the blackboard and is not a touch screen.

Respondents reported challenges and difficulties for students to independently explore new concepts or activities, often preferring non-educational games. Excessive screen time, particularly for low-functioning students, poses a significant concern, necessitating a balanced approach that includes hands-on learning, social interaction, and physical movement. The introduction of new technological platforms often results in a loss of instructional time due to the need for extensive teaching on how to use these tools effectively. Furthermore, students with sensory and behavioral issues require specialized approaches to maintain focus and manage behavior

“Lathan (2022) emphasizes that technology is continuously reshaping how we work, play, create, and communicate. Advances in digital technology are also transforming education, creating new opportunities for teachers to engage young learners. The excitement surrounding technologies such as assistive technology, augmented and virtual reality, high-tech collaboration tools, gamification, podcasting, video blogging, 3D printing, artificial intelligence, and personalized learning reflects a global competitive drive in the business sector.

Additionally, respondents noted diverse student reactions to applied technology in the classroom. While some students resist trying new technologies or are fixated on a particular one, teachers affirmed that the use of these technologies should be balanced and neutral. Despite frequent use of data to monitor student progress, there is a recognized need for evaluation tools .

Neumann et al (2019) discusses frameworks and tools for classroom assessment that significantly influence teaching practices and student achievement. Effective assessment is essential for fostering positive learning experiences and achieving academic success. Recent reports from the United States and Australia advocate for developing systems that utilize new technologies to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of educational assessments. The review examines digital -age assessment factors from both assessment for learning (AfL) and assessment of learning (AoL) perspectives, noting that technology offers substantial opportunities to enhance test administration, scoring, reporting, interpretation, and curriculum alignment to personalize learning. Future assessment systems must address challenges related to developmental appropriateness, item development, psychometric validation, and teacher implementation. Success will depend on close collaboration among educators, students, and policymakers in the design, development, and utilizing application of technology-based assessments.

An article published in *Educ Sci* in 2023 titled “Enhancing Student Engagement: Harnessing ‘AIED’ Power in Hybrid Education—A Review Analysis,” highlights the need to improve educational systems and practices by exploring the role of artificial intelligence (AI) in providing immediate feedback on student learning and engagement. The research conducted shortly after the pandemic suggests that AI could be beneficial for delivering direct feedback on student progress and addresses the diversity of learners and their varying learning styles.

Conclusion

Many teacher-respondents were aged between 31 and 50 years. Majority of the respondents were female and possessed over 10 years of teaching experience. Additionally, most respondents hold a bachelor's degree, while a small percentage completed graduate studies. (1) Teachers often utilize educational online videos followed by independent online programs and sometimes use gamified online programs and interactive technology. (2) There was a significant difference in teacher's utilization of online independent programs and interactive technology when grouped according to age, sex, and years of teaching experience. (3) Learners were often engaged when interactive technology and educational online videos were employed in the classroom and sometimes engaged when gamified online learning and online independent programs were used in instruction. (4) Additionally, respondents indicated a lack of tools to evaluate learner engagement when integrating technology. This gap highlights the need for developing effective assessment tools. The researcher planned to create such a tool to serve as a basis for enhancing learner engagement in the classroom. (5) Learners were more engaged when younger female teachers integrated applied technology into instruction. (6) Teachers reported challenges on learners' proficiency in digital literacy skills and revealed that there is no specific assessment tool to measure learners' engagement.

Therefore, there was considerable variation in teachers' utilization of applied technology, with educational online videos being predominantly used, while interactive technologies were less frequently employed. In contrast, learners showed a higher frequency of engagement with interactive technologies. This disparity underscored the necessity to develop a technology assessment tool and to enhance the digital literacy of young learners. Furthermore, it was imperative to provide teachers with contemporary strategies for the effective integration of technology into instructional settings. Addressing these discrepancies could significantly enhance the efficacy of interactive technology and improve overall learner engagement.

Based on the foregoing findings and conclusion, the researcher hereby recommends the following.

(1) The School District ICT Department must develop an assessment tool to evaluate the effectiveness and measure learner's engagement with applied technology in the classroom. There is a need to promote a culture of knowledge sharing among teachers, where they can exchange best practices and successful strategies for integrating technology. (2) Instructional Coaches or administrators must offer specialized workshops or short courses to address the specific needs of teachers at different experience levels and subject areas. (3) Curriculum Developers must integrate Digital Literacy as part of the curriculum ensuring all learners are digitally proficient and literate. (4) Educators and teachers must create opportunities for learners to practice responsible digital literacy and set expectations whenever possible. Additionally, regularly soliciting feedback from students regarding their experiences with technology is a must to make informed decisions about instructional adjustments. The community should promote a positive attitude toward technology by highlighting the benefits of technology in enhancing learning and demonstrating its practical applications in real-world scenarios. (5) The Coordinator of Technology and Data Coordinator must analyze data progress to ensure the effectiveness of the applied technology program every quarter and determine which applied technology should be utilized. (6) The Public Education Department should invest in interactive technology tools and resources that have been shown to significantly engage learners. Increase Access to Interactive Technology. Examples include interactive whiteboards, educational apps, and collaborative online platforms. (7) The Federal and State government and /or local support must ensure equitable access to modern educational technology including those in underfunded or rural areas. By implementing these recommendations, schools can create a more engaging and effective learning environment that leverages the full potential of technology to enhance student outcomes

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